

Holistic evaluation of PHA extraction methods: insights from LCA, eLCC, and physico-chemical characterization

B. Vázquez-Vázquez*, S. Martínez-Rey*, A. Val del Río*, M. Lazzari**, and A. Hospido*

* CRETUS, Department of Chemical Engineering, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain

(E-mail: braisvazquez.vazquez@usc.es; saramartinez.rey@usc.es; mangeles.val@usc.es; almudena.hospido@usc.es)

** CIQUS, Department of Physical Chemistry, Universidade de Santiago de Compostela, 15782 Santiago de Compostela, Spain

(E-mail: massimo.lazzari@usc.es)

Abstract

This study evaluates various extraction methods of polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) from bacterial biomass, specifically chemical digestion and solvent extraction. Life cycle assessment (LCA) and environmental life cycle cost (eLCC) methodologies were used to select those with the best environmental and economic performance resulting in those based in chemical digestion using NaOH and H₂O₂. Additionally, the characteristics of PHA extracted with both methods were also evaluated in PHA-rich biomass, obtained from a process with a mixed culture and with used cooking oil (UCO) as substrate. The results of the physicochemical characterization of the extracted PHA show that NaOH stands out for its ability to denature proteins (breaking the biomass to facilitate PHA extraction) and to remove triacylglycerides (TAGs) by saponification.

Keywords (maximum 6 in alphabetical order)

downstream; DSC; environmental Life Cycle Costing; FTIR; Life Cycle Assessment; polyhydroxyalkanoates

INTRODUCTION

The level of circularity in the plastic sector in Europe in 2022 is around 14%, far below the 2050 target of 78% (Plastics Europe, 2022). Additionally, biobased and biodegradable polymers (BPs) account for less than 1% of global plastic production, with polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs) emerging as a promising solution due to their biodegradability, UV resistance, and thermoplasticity (Sharma et al., 2021). The national-funded project ECOPOLYVER aims to valorise lipidic waste from the food industry by producing PHAs by the PRETENACC technology (TRL 5), i.e. a single aerobic unit (Argiz et al., 2022). The resultant PHAs will be used for food packaging items replacing there fossil-based plastics like polypropylene (PP) and low-density polyethylene (LDPE), and to do so bioplastics (BPs) must offer comparable properties, improved environmental performance, and economic viability (European Commission, 2021). However, the life cycle of PHAs faces critical bottlenecks in the downstream process, particularly during the extraction stage, which typically involves high energy and chemicals consumption. Several extraction methods such as solvent dissolution, mechanical disruption, chemical digestion, or enzymatic degradation (Pérez-Rivero et al., 2019; Saavedra del Oso et al., 2021) are available and its selection is critical as it not only influences the life cycle environmental and economic performance but also determines the yield, purity, and overall quality of the extracted material.

This study evaluates different extraction methods where (i) life cycle assessment (LCA) and environmental life cycle costing (eLCC) are used to screen those methods with the best environmental and economic performance (Nessi et al., 2021); (ii) laboratory tests are performed with the selected extraction methods to perform physicochemical characterization of the obtained PHA, and (iii) the method with the best balance in terms of PHA yield, purity, physico-chemical properties, and environmental and economic performance is selected for implementation in the scaling up of the

process, which is carried out in the POLYGO1 project.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For a comprehensive literature review of PHA extraction methods with potential for scale-up was conducted, nine extraction processes were identified (Table 1):

Table 1. Identified PHA extraction methods.

Extraction process	Extraction method	Inhibitor	Extraction agent	Source
E1a E1b	Chemical digestion	NaClO	NaOH	(Salvatori et al., 2023)
		H ₂ SO ₄		
E2a E2b	Chemical digestion	NaClO	H ₂ O ₂	(Salvatori et al., 2023)
		H ₂ SO ₄		
E3a E3b	Chemical digestion	NaClO	NaOH + H ₂ O ₂	(Salvatori et al., 2023)
		H ₂ SO ₄		
E4a E4b	Chemical digestion	NaClO	Ethyl acetate	(Salvatori et al., 2023)
		H ₂ SO ₄		
E5	Solvent extraction	-	BuOH	WOW! project ¹

LCA and eLCC were then performed; the functional unit was set as 1 kg of extracted PHA and a gate-to-gate approach was established.

A midpoint approach was followed with SimaPro software (v9.6) for potential global warming impact category. The eLCC framework introduces, for the first time to the best of our knowledge, the simultaneous inclusion of operational costs (OPEX), capital costs (CAPEX), and external environmental costs (ECC), which represents the economic cost of mitigating environmental damage, as proposed by Seider et al. (2017).

PHA extraction tests were performed using NaOH (E1a and E1b) and H₂O₂ (E2a and E2b). These methods were tested on a biomass, obtained from a biological process with mixed culture and used cooking oil (UCO) as carbon source, containing 28.30 ± 1.88 wt % PHA and 22.75 ± 1.47 wt % triacylglycerides (TAGs). The biomass was acidified, centrifuged, and oven-dried before extraction. PHA and TAG quantification was conducted using gas chromatography (GC), while thermal properties were evaluated by thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) and differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy and proton nuclear magnetic resonance (¹H-NMR) spectroscopy were used to assess PHA purity and composition.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Environmental and economic screening

The LCA results illustrate the overall global warming impacts of the different extraction methods (Figure 1a), along with the contributions of each stage in the process (Figure 1b). Other impact categories, such as terrestrial acidification, ecotoxicity, and human toxicity, are included in a paper that is currently under publication. The E5 was certainly excluded due its high energy demands for heating, filtering, and drying. Similarly, chemical digestion processes using EtAc (E4a and E4b) showed poor environmental performance, particularly due to the chemicals used at the dissolution stage. In contrast, processes using NaOH (E1a and E1b), H₂O₂ (E2a and E2b), and both together (E3a and E3b) exhibited more favourable environmental profiles, with global warming potentials as low as 0.07–0.88 kg CO₂-eq/kg PHA. This makes them preferable extraction methods, outperforming better environmental performance compared to many other alternatives reported in literature (0.81–

¹ <https://vb.nweurope.eu/projects/project-search/wow-wider-business-opportunities-for-raw-materials-from-wastewater/>

29.46 CO₂-eq/kg PHA; (López-Abelairas et al., 2015; Saavedra del Oso et al., 2021)).

Figure 1. Characterization (a) results and contribution analysis (b) of E1-5 extraction processes.

Processes E4a and E4b have the greatest economic impacts with over 50% corresponding to environmental external costs (Figure 2), due to the high cost of ethyl acetate (960 €/tonne (Chemanalyst, 2024)). At this point, the benefits of using solvent (E5) or ethyl acetate (E4a and E4b) instead of NaOH or H₂O₂ are outweighed in both impact and cost categories. Nevertheless, NaOH and H₂O₂ processes show significantly better cost-efficiency, with costs ranging from 0.39–0.51 €/kg PHA.

Figure 2. Economic evaluation of processes, per kg of extracted PHA. AD, UC, mC, LC, and MC are referred to annual depreciation, utilities, materials, labour and maintenance costs respectively. EEC refer to the economic cost of repairing the environmental damage of each process.

PHA quality assessment

In addition to offering better environmental and economic performance, PHA must provide comparable quality to PP and LDPE to be a potential substitute. This quality is highly dependent on the extraction method, as demonstrated by the characterization results:

- **NaOH-based method:** demonstrated 87 wt. % recovery of PHA, with a purity of 68 wt. %. The NaOH treatment facilitate the saponification of TAGs, leading to a significant reduction in TAG concentration from 23 wt. % to 9 wt. %. Additionally, although the FTIR spectra showed peaks consistent with bacterial residues, these were reduced from 49 wt. % to 10 wt. %.
- **H₂O₂-based method:** achieved almost complete recovery (~100 %) but resulted in the lowest purity (34 wt. % PHA) due to the presence of residual bacteria (45 wt. %) and TAGs (21 wt. %). Besides, the oxidative nature of H₂O₂ may have disrupted the PHA structure, leading to lower crystallinity (10%) compared to NaOH-base methods (52%).

In addition, ¹H-NMR spectra revealed that all extraction methods produced PHA copolymers, with characteristic peaks for hydroxyvalerate (HV) and hydroxybutyrate (HB).

CONCLUSIONS

This study indicates that chemical digestion by NaOH and/or H₂O₂ are the most promising extraction methods for PHA in terms of both environmental and economic performance. Furthermore, the laboratory results with a specific biomass, containing PHA and TAG, showed that NaOH provided the best balance between PHA recovery, purity and thermal properties, making it the preferred choice for scale-up.

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